

ISSN 2181-8622

Manufacturing technology problems

**Scientific and Technical Journal
Namangan Institute of
Engineering and Technology**

**Volume 8
Issue 1
2023**

Hong Kong Polytechnic University

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INVESTIGATION OF THE INFLUENCE OF SPEED MODES OF THE COMBED DRUM ON THE QUALITY INDICATORS OF THE TAPE

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Abstract:

Objective. In this research work, using the system of modern technological equipment, the effect of the parameters of the main working organs of the combed machine on the quality indicators and fiber length of the wick obtained from the selection of medium fiber cotton was studied. It was determined that the staple length of the fiber increased by 2.07 mm at a speed of 350 min⁻¹. The purpose of the study is to study the influence of the comb speed of the combed drum on the quality parameters of the sliver and the staple length of the fiber.

Results. In the experiment, the influence of the speed of rotation of the comb drum on the quality parameters of the combed sliver was studied. As a result, when the rotation speed of the combed drum is 350 min⁻¹, the coefficient of variation of the combed sliver is improved, the staple length of the fiber is increased by 2.07 mm.

Conclusion. The distribution of the mass of fibers over the cross section of the tape tape corresponds to the normal distribution law $Cm/Um=1.25 (2.72/2.32)$. Unevenness of the combed sliver in 1 m segments decreases with a decrease in the speed of the combed drum, and with an increase in its speed it increases by 12%. The clogging of the batt decreases with an increase in the speed of the drum, in which the number of defects per 1g of tape is 26 i.e. the minimum value of the compared options.

Keywords: Combing machine, fibers, ribbon, lap, combing drum, coefficient of variation, unevenness, staple mass length, knots, skin with fiber, litter.

Introduction. Every year, the range of manufactured textile products is replenished with new names of goods that are in great demand both on the domestic and foreign markets. Thanks to the introduction of high-performance modern technologies into the industry, the export of products of the industry's enterprises has grown 110 times compared to the first years of independence. Today, light industry products are exported to more than 60 countries of the world, and the sales geography is constantly expanding [1-4].

Combed cotton yarn traditionally has a stable and high demand not only at domestic textile enterprises, but also abroad, where it is used to produce a high-quality range of products. The equipment installed in recent years at the cotton-spinning factories of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the process of complex modernization and re-equipment of the textile industry enterprises allows, according to its technical characteristics, to obtain high-quality combed yarn from medium-staple cotton [5-8].

At the same time, combed yarn from medium-staple cotton is increasingly being used in the production of textile products, successfully replacing yarn from long-staple cotton [9-14].

Thus, the replacement of long-staple cotton varieties with medium-staple selection varieties in the production of yarn for fabrics and knitwear is a very urgent task facing textile enterprises around the world, including for the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In connection with the above, it is of interest to study issues related to improving the preparation of the combed sliver on combing machines, as well as the influence of the speed modes of the combed drum on

the quality indicators of the combed sliver using medium fiber cotton.

The purpose of this work is to study the influence of the frequency of rotation of the combed drum on the quality indicators of the combed sliver. To study the influence of the speed modes of the combed drum on the quality indicators of the tape, an experimental study was carried out on a Comber E66 comber by RIETER, installed in the production conditions of JV LLC TEXTILE FINANCE KHOREZM.

The filling parameters of the machine under study, speed modes and technological wiring of the working bodies corresponded to the operating instructions for the machine. For the production of semi-finished products and yarn, factory sorting was used, consisting of cotton fiber of type 4, class I, class "Yakhshi", breeding variety Bukhara 102. Experimental studies were carried out in three versions with a speed of the third receiving drum of 300, 350, 400 min⁻¹. Processing of raw materials was carried out according to the technological chain of modern equipment from RIETER (Switzerland).

Methods and results. To assess the quality of semi-finished products and yarn, modern laboratory equipment from Uster was used. The results obtained from testing semi-finished products and yarns were evaluated by comparison with HTD norms and norms according to Uster-Statistics [15-17].

The quality indicators of semi-finished products are shown in Table 1. Before the research, the quality of the carding, ribbon tape and feeding laps from the tape connecting machine was checked.

From Table 1. it can be seen that the quality of the semi-finished products developed for the experiments is high, which is associated with the use

Table 1.

Quality indicators of initial semi-finished products

No	The name of indicators	Card tape	Tape with "0" head	Canvas
1	Linear density, tex	5900	5000	73750
2	The coefficient of variation, %			
	- by 1 m segments	1,3	0,84	0,56
	- by 3 m segments	0,8	0,59	-
3	Roughness in section %			
	-linear, Um	2,72	2,32	1,54
	-coefficient of variation Cv	3,41	2,90	
	Level of Ust	39	12	
4	The number of defects in 1 g of carding			
	sliver pcs:	68		
	nodules	57		
	Skin with fiber	9		
	rubbish	2		

Modern equipment. The quality of the card sliver meets the 39% level according to Uster-Statistics, the sliver with the "O" head - 12% the level of Uster. The distribution of the mass of fibers over the cross section of the tape tape corresponds to the normal distribution law $C_m/U_m=1.25$ (2.72/2.32)

Square uneven laps on 1 meter segments 0.56% compared options.

A combed sliver was produced from the resulting laps on a Comber E66 comber from Rieter (Switzerland).

The combed sliver of each option was tested on the Uster-Tester 5-S400. The clogging and length of the fiber in the tape were determined on the Uster-Afis-Pro device [18-21].

The results of measurements of the main parameters are shown in Table 2. Table 2 shows that the unevenness of the combed sliver in 1 m segments decreases with a decrease in the speed of the combed drum, and with an increase in its speed it increases by 12%.

Table 2.

Main indicators of the quality of the combed sliver

The name of indicators	Comb drum rotation frequency, min ⁻¹		
	300	350	400
1 Tape linear density, ktex	5,02	5,01	5,0
2 Coefficient of variation by segments Main indicators of the quality of the combed sliver			
	1,95	1,73	2,1
	2m 1,50	1,33	1,61
	3m 1,32	1,15	1,40
3 Ribbon irregularity			
-linear, Um	3,60	3,34	3,48
-coefficient of variation, Cv	4,5	4,18	4,36
4 Staple mass length of fibers, mm	34,26	36,33	35,40
modal mass length, mm	31,03	33,06	32,15
5 Short fiber content, %	4,8	3,9	4,6
6 The number of defects per 1 g of the tape, pcs	29	26	30
knots	28	25	29
waste	0	3	1

A decrease in the length of the fiber by 1 mm [4-6] with a large staple mass length causes a decrease in the specific breaking load of the yarn when tested with a skein by 3–5%, and with a smaller staple mass length of the fiber, by 6–10%.

Figure 1. Staple length of fibers and the quality of defects per 1 g of tape by options

From Table 1. and Fig. 1. It can be seen that in variant 2, the maximum staple mass is the length of the fibers at the speed of the combed drum $n_{gr}=350 \text{ min}^{-1}$ (Lsht 36.33 mm). The minimum value of the staple weight of length in 1 option (Lpcs 34, 26 mm). Comparing the values of the staple length in options 1 and 2, we see that the speed of the drum has a decisive influence on this indicator.

The clogging of the batt decreases with an increase in the speed of the drum, which can be seen in option 2 in Fig. 1. in which the number of defects per 1g of tape is 26 i.e. the minimum value of the compared options.

The above studies allow us to conclude that an increase in the speed of

the combed drum leads to an increase in the staple length of the fiber and an increase in the specific breaking load of the yarn.

Conclusion. 1. The distribution of the mass of fibers over the cross section of the tape corresponds to the normal distribution law $C_m/U_m=1.25$ (2.72/2.32);

2. Unevenness of the combed sliver in 1 m segments decreases with a decrease in the speed of the combed drum, and with an increase in its speed it increases by 12%.

3. The clogging of the batt decreases with an increase in the speed of the drum, in which the number of defects per 1g of tape is 26 i.e. the minimum value of the compared options.

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DETERMINATION OF THE GEOMETRIC AND KINEMATIC PARAMETERS OF THE DEVELOPED CHAIN GEAR FOR THE 2SB-10 DRYER

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Abstract:

Objective. The article presents the calculated data for determining the geometric and kinematic parameters of the developed chain transmission for the 2SB-10 cotton dryer.

Methods. According to the developed drive scheme, the beater was assembled with a leading drive of the drum, consisting mainly of an electric motor with a power of 7.5 kW, a rotation speed of 1430 rpm, a gearbox with a gear ratio of 1 to 31.5.

Results. Therefore, the value of the chain pitch is limited by the maximum allowable value of the angular velocity of the small sprocket.

Conclusion. The given calculation data are necessary for the manufacture and assembly of the developed chain transmission for the drum dryer 2 SB-10.

Keywords: chain drive, diameter, drive, sprocket, center distance, pitch, number of teeth.

Introduction. Taking into account the analysis of previous work in the laboratory of drying, cleaning of raw cotton, "Cotton Industry Scientific Center" JSC developed a drive scheme for a 2SB-10 cotton dryer, the scheme of which is shown in Fig. 1 [1].

The advantage of the developed drive is that the generated variable loads from the side of the dryer drum are ground using the chain drive (that is, with the chain length adjustment and the choice of center distance) [2].

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**“SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL JOURNAL OF
NAMANGAN INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERING AND
TECHNOLOGY”**

**The editorial was typed and paginated in the computer center
Paper format A4. Size 20 conditional printing plate**

**The copy must be taken from the "Scientific and Technical Journal of the
Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology"**